

Default Question Block

You are receiving this survey as our initial investigation identified you as a contributor on Github. This survey should take approximately 5 minutes to complete.

With this survey, we want to know your opinion regarding the practices pertaining to inclusivity in Open Source projects.

Your participation is voluntary and confidential. You can withdraw at any time. We do not record any identifying information.

This survey is conducted by a team of computer science researchers. The results of this survey will be used in a scientific publication. Should you be interested in being informed about the outcome of this study or any resulting publication, please contact

By clicking the button below, you acknowledge that your participation in the study is voluntary, that you are 18 years of age, and that you are aware that you may choose to terminate your participation in the study at any time and for any reason.

- I consent, begin the study
- I do not consent

Block 1

Are you a professional software developer paid by any organization?

- Yes
- No

How many people work at your organization?

- 1-49

- 50-999
- 1,000-5,000
- More than 5,000

How much experience do you have in open source software?

- Less than 3 months
- 3 to 6 months
- 7 months to 1 year
- More than 1 year

Is inclusivity evaluation a part of your software development process?

- Yes
- No

Block 2

Based on your experience with software development, what do you think are some of the challenges with ensuring inclusivity in software?

- Lack of awareness about inclusivity and its importance
- Additional costs of ensuring inclusivity
- Lack of guidelines to ensure inclusivity
- Lack of tools
- Lack of support from management
- Other, please specify

Do you use any inclusivity guidelines?

- If yes, please specify

No

What are the tools / techniques that you are using to check for inclusivity?

- The GenderMag Method
- The GenderMag Recorder's Assistant tool
- Other, please specify

Block 3

Anything else you want to add?